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On the Structure and Redox Behavior of Ni and Cu Single Atoms Supported on Carbon Nitride

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ABSTRACT

Single-atom catalysts (SACs) offer molecular-level control in heterogeneous catalysis, but their activity depends on whether the support can sustain metal-centered redox cycling. Here, Ni and Cu single atoms on carbon nitride (CN_x) are compared to determine how coordination geometry governs redox reversibility and photocatalytic performance. EPR/ENDOR spectroscopy, x-ray absorption, and DFT identify a unique edge MN₄ site, composed of three sp² nitrogens and one bridging sp³ nitrogen, as the binding motif for both metals. While Ni and Cu occupy the same MN₄ site in the oxidized state, their redox behavior diverges. Ni preserves a distorted square–planar geometry and undergoes fully reversible Ni²⁺/Ni⁺ cycling. In contrast, Cu collapses upon reduction to a low-coordinate Cu⁺ species that cannot be re-oxidized. This structural mismatch suppresses catalytic turnover. Accordingly, Ni@CN_x efficiently promotes photoredox C–N, C–O, and C–S couplings, whereas Cu@CN_x remains inactive. Catalytic performance thus depends on redox compatibility within a rigid binding pocket, rather than on metal identity alone.

Isolated metal atoms are inherently catalytic [1], yet their reactivity is governed by the first and subsequent coordination spheres provided by molecular ligands or solid supports [2]. Single-atom catalysts (SACs) exploit this principle by anchoring individual ions in atomically defined environments [3], combining the geometric precision of molecular complexes with the robustness of heterogeneous materials [4]. These systems have become valuable for a number of relevant (photo)catalytic reactions [5–8], although their performance ultimately hinges on the redox behavior of the embedded metal centers [9].

Carbon nitride (CN_x), formally built from heptazine and/or triazine units, is widely used as a support, yet its atomic structure depends sensitively on preparation conditions [10, 11], and the nature of the metal binding pockets remains debated. Different sites for metal coordination have been proposed, usually involving nitrogen ligand atoms in idealized heptazine units [12, 13]. However, recent work by Vilè and Pacchioni [14] has shown that in the case of prototypical Ni^{II}, the spectroscopic evidences can only be reconciled considering square–planar like sites available at edge boundaries of oligomeric structures. Moreover, essentially

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no experimental information exists on how these putative sites reorganise upon metal redox cycling.

In redox-active SACs, the central issue is therefore not only the identity of the binding site but also whether the site can preserve its geometry throughout the catalytic redox cycle and, most importantly, how its geometric rigidity may constrain the electronic configuration of the metal during the redox cycle. This is the key question addressed in the present work.

This concept echoes the entatic-state model in bioinorganic chemistry, where protein scaffolds pre-organize the coordination environment to minimize the reorganisation energy associated with metal-centred redox transformations [15, 16]. Molecular inorganic systems provide analogous examples: subtle ligand-induced changes in coordination geometry can dramatically shift redox potentials, notably in Cu^{II} complexes where modulation of the N_4 ligand field governs the accessibility of the $\text{Cu}^{\text{II}}/\text{Cu}^{\text{I}}$ couple [17]. These examples suggest that the CN_x scaffold may enforce distinct redox trajectories on different metals, stabilizing some oxidation states while disfavoring others.

We show that this redox behavior differs markedly for Ni and Cu single atoms supported on CN_x . Across a series of photoredox model reactions for C–N, C–O, and C–S coupling, relevant to the synthesis of key pharmaceutical, agrochemical, and materials precursors [7, 18–20], Ni@CN_x exhibits robust catalytic activity, whereas Cu@CN_x remains largely inactive. Combined experimental and computational analyses reveal that Ni maintains a square-planar MN_4 environment and undergoes efficient $\text{Ni}^{\text{II}}/\text{Ni}^{\text{I}}$ cycling, while Cu collapses from a four-coordinate site to a two-coordinate Cu^{I} centre that cannot be re-oxidized. This divergence, rooted in the electronic contrast between Ni^{I} (d^9) and Cu^{I} (d^{10}), directly dictates their opposite photocatalytic performance in cross-coupling reactions.

To elucidate the geometric and electronic structure of the two SACs, we performed x-ray absorption spectroscopy (XAS) and electron paramagnetic resonance (EPR) investigations, carrying out both measurements on the very same sample under identical preparation and handling conditions (Supporting Information, sections S1.2 and S1.3). Details on the stepwise synthesis of CN_x catalysts are provided in the Supporting Information (Sections S1.1 and S1.4–S1.7). The Ni K-edge position in as-prepared Ni@CN_x coincides with that of NiO, confirming a +2 oxidation state (Figure 1a, black line), while, under the same conditions, Cu@CN_x exhibits a distinct pre-edge peak at 8982.5 eV, indicative of the partial presence of Cu^{I} species (Figure 1b).

Extended x-ray absorption fine structure (EXAFS) data (Figure 1c,d; Figures S2 and S4) reveal the absence of metal-metal scattering peaks at distances characteristic of Ni–Ni (2.95 Å in NiO, Table S3) or Cu–Cu (3.04 Å in Cu_2O) in both materials, demonstrating that Ni and Cu are atomically dispersed. Consistently, energy-dispersive x-ray spectroscopy (EDS) mapping and high-angle annular dark-field STEM (HAADF–STEM) show a homogeneous metal distribution with no detectable clustering (Figure S6).

The photocatalytic behavior of Ni@CN_x and Cu@CN_x SACs with the same metal loading was evaluated under identical conditions

using photoredox model reactions of C–N, C–O and C–S coupling between aryl halides and suitable nitrogen-, oxygen-, and sulfur-based molecular precursors. These experiments represented the starting point of our study. The couplings proceed via a dual photoredox mechanism in which visible-light irradiation (456 nm) of CN_x generates photoexcited electrons that are transferred to the metal species (Ni^{II} or Cu^{II}) through single-electron transfer (SET) [7]. The reduced metal then undergoes oxidative addition with the aryl halide, thereby initiating the redox catalytic cycle. Catalytic tests (Supporting Information Section S2, Table S1) comparing two aryl halides (Br and I) revealed that Ni@CN_x is highly effective: it promoted C–N coupling in 87%–89% isolated yield (75% after 8 h for iodides) and achieved similarly efficient C–O (70% \pm 4%) and C–S (58% \pm 9%) formations (Supporting Information Section S2, Table S2). In sharp contrast, Cu@CN_x did not afford any cross-coupled products in any of these reactions, producing only minor dehalogenation by-products (Supporting Information Section S2, Tables S1 and S2).

Such large differences in catalytic activity cannot originate from textural effects [21], as the two materials exhibit comparable surface areas and porosity, as confirmed by N_2 physisorption (Figure S5). Moreover, since homogeneous Cu catalysts readily promote C–N couplings [22–24], the divergent behavior observed here shows that the determining factor is not the intrinsic reactivity of Cu versus Ni, but rather how their redox chemistry is constrained within the CN_x scaffold. This raises a central mechanistic issue, namely that two closely related d-block ions with the same oxidation states give rise to entirely different catalytic outcomes when anchored on CN_x .

To address this question, we disentangled the intrinsic redox response of Ni and Cu from the complexities of the photocatalytic environment by probing the $\text{Ni}^{\text{II}}/\text{Ni}^{\text{I}}$ and $\text{Cu}^{\text{II}}/\text{Cu}^{\text{I}}$ couples under idealized solid-gas conditions. Using EPR, ENDOR, and XAS, supported by DFT, we monitored the redox transitions generated through H_2/O_2 cycling and selectively interrogated the paramagnetic intermediates (Ni^{I} and Cu^{II}). This approach enabled a direct comparison of the efficiency and reversibility of the two redox couples, and of the geometric rearrangements accompanying reduction.

XAS measurements at the Ni and Cu K-edges (Figure 1) showed that as-prepared Ni@CN_x contains exclusively Ni^{II} , with an edge position matching that of NiO. After H_2 reduction, the Ni K-edge shifts by \sim 1 eV to lower energy, consistent with formation of Ni^{I} , while a pre-edge shoulder at \sim 8335 eV, diagnostic of square-planar coordination, remains in both oxidation states [25, 26]. Cu@CN_x displays a markedly different behavior: the pre-edge feature at 8982.5 eV, associated with Cu^{I} , increases substantially upon reduction, indicating full conversion to Cu^{I} . EXAFS analysis further shows that reduced Cu@CN_x adopts a two-coordinate, nearly linear Cu^{I} N_2 first-shell geometry, in line with the preference of the closed-shell $3d^{10}$ configuration for low coordination numbers (Supporting Information section S1.2).

EPR spectroscopy was used to follow redox cycling and probe—in a highly selective way—the local coordination of the paramagnetic intermediates, exploiting the $3d^9$ configuration of Ni^{I} and Cu^{II} . $\text{Cu}^{\text{II}}@CN_x$ (0.06 wt%, ICP-OES) exhibits the expected axial $S = \frac{1}{2}$ spectrum, with $g_{\parallel} > g_{\perp} > g_e$ and well-resolved

FIGURE 1 | Normalized Ni (a) and Cu (b) K-edge XANES spectra measured on as-prepared and reduced Ni@CN_x and Cu@CN_x catalysts, respectively. For comparison, the spectra of the reference Ni compounds (crystalline NiO as reference for Ni^{II} and Ni metal foil) in (a) and the spectra of the reference Cu compounds (crystalline Cu₂O as reference for Cu^I and Cu metal foil) in (b) are added. The spectra are shifted vertically for clarity. The Fourier transform magnitude of the k-weighted Ni K-edge EXAFS spectra and the k³-weighted Cu K-edge EXAFS spectra of the as-prepared and the reduced catalyst, calculated in the k range of 3–8 Å⁻¹ for Ni and 3–12 Å⁻¹ for Cu, are shown in (c) and (d), respectively.

^{63/65}Cu ($I = 3/2$) hyperfine splitting, consistent with a $d_{x^2-y^2}$ SOMO (Figure 2a). The high-field region reveals additional ligand hyperfine couplings, which based on ENDOR data correspond to two pairs of equivalent ¹⁴N nuclei ($I = 1$) with $|A_z| \approx 45$ and 51 MHz (Table 1, Figure 3). These couplings indicate coordination to four nearly equivalent N donors in a square-planar environment, analogous to porphyrinic Cu^{II} complexes [27].

Quantitative EPR indicates that ~60% of Cu is initially present as Cu^{II}, indicating partial reduction to EPR-silent Cu^I, in accordance with XAS data (Figure 1b). Increasing Cu loading up to 1.2 wt%

(Figure S16) shows no significant changes in EPR-active Cu^{II}, suggesting a constant number of isolated Cu^{II} single-atom sites ($\sim 1 \times 10^{19}$ sites g⁻¹).

After reduction under H₂, the Cu^{II} signal vanishes and is not restored upon reoxidation (Figure 2b), demonstrating irreversible collapse of Cu^{II}→Cu^I within the CN_x pocket. By contrast, Ni^{II}@CN_x is EPR-silent due to its low-spin d⁸ configuration, but reduction generates a strongly anisotropic Ni^I (3d⁹) EPR signal (Figure 2c), characteristic of a $d_{x^2y^2}$ SOMO [28], and quantitative EPR shows that ~85% of Ni participates in the

FIGURE 2 | (a) X-band CW-EPR spectra of Ni@CN_x recorded after oxidizing or reducing treatments as noted; (b) Double integrated intensity of the EPR spectra presented in panel (a); (c) X-band CW-EPR spectra of Cu@CN_x recorded after oxidizing or reducing treatments as noted; (d) corresponding integrated intensities. All spectra were recorded at 77K. The asterisk indicates a CN_x defect.

TABLE 1 | Spin-Hamiltonian parameters for Ni^I and Cu^{II}@CN_x catalysts and molecular analogues. Hyperfine constants are given in units of MHz.

	g_x	g_y	g_z	$^M A_x$	$^M A_y$	$^M A_z$	$^N A_x$	$^N A_y$	$^N A_z$ [c]	ref
Ni@CN _x	2.074 ± 0.012 ^[a]	2.095 ± 0.013 ^[a]	2.355 ± 0.04 ^[a]				11 ± 1	11 ± 1	14 ± 1	This
	2.066 ± 0.024 ^[b]	2.120 ± 0.035 ^[b]	2.370 ± 0.06 ^[b]				19 ± 1	19 ± 1	22 ± 1	work
							23 ± 1	23 ± 1	26 ± 1	
Ni@CN	2.059	2.114	2.339				27 ± 1	27 ± 1	30 ± 1	[29]
Ni ^I F430 [d]	2.063	2.063	2.244				22.0	26.5	31.0 34.0	[30]
							26.5	27.0		
MCRred1 ^[e]	2.060	2.070	2.2485				22.5 27.0	25.0	31.5 36.0	[30]
								30.6		
MCRox2 ^[e]	2.125	2.140	2.227							[31]
MCRred2 ^[e]	2.1753	2.2313	2.2869				11.8	13.5	16.0	[31]
							21.0	20.2	26.2	
							24.0	23.2	26.6	
Cu@CN _x	2.052 ± 0.01	2.052 ± 0.01	2.205 ± 0.001	50 ± 5	50 ± 5	550 ± 5	35 ± 3	30 ± 3	45 ± 3	This
							44 ± 3	40 ± 3	51 ± 3	
CuPc [f]	2.039 ± 0.01	2.039 ± 0.01	2.157 ± 0.01	83 ± 5	83 ± 5	648 ± 5	44.7 ± 0.5	45.4 ± 0.5	56.5 ± 0.5	[32]
CuTPP [f]	2.045	2.045	2.190	102.7 ± 3	102.7 ± 3	615 ± 3	42.8	44.06	54.2	[33]

^aAbundance = 36%.

^bAbundance = 64%.

^cThe $^N A_z$ component is oriented along the $g_{x,y}$ axes and lies in the equatorial plane of the molecule.

^dNi(I) Form of Cofactor F4301 of Methanobacterium thermoautotrophicum.

^eNi(I) in Methyl-coenzyme M reductase.

^fCu(II) phthalocyanine.

^gCu(II) tetraphenylporphyrin.

FIGURE 3 | (a)–(c) Experimental and simulated Q-band ($\nu = 33.83104$ GHz) EDNMR spectra of $\text{Ni}^{\text{I}}@\text{CN}_x$ recorded at $\mathbf{B} = 1026.6$ mT (a), $\mathbf{B} = 1134.0$ mT (b), $\mathbf{B} = 1156.3$ mT (c); (d)–(f) Experimental and simulated Q-band ($\nu = 33.82373$ GHz) Davies ENDOR spectra of $\text{Cu}^{\text{II}}@\text{CN}_x$ recorded at $\mathbf{B} = 1080.0$ mT (d), $\mathbf{B} = 1140.0$ mT (e), $\mathbf{B} = 1170.0$ mT. All spectra were recorded at 10 K. Simulation of the ^{14}N nuclei is in yellow, while the simulation of the ^1H interaction is shown in pink.

$\text{Ni}^{\text{II}}/\text{Ni}^{\text{I}}$ transition. Crucially, the Ni^{I} signal is fully restored upon oxidation, and repeated redox cycling is possible without loss of intensity (Figure 2d). XRD patterns recorded prior and after the redox cycles are superimposable (Figure S7) demonstrating that the structure of the catalyst is preserved.

EPR measurements performed on catalysts recovered after reaction showed that $\text{Ni}@\text{CN}_x$ retains its redox activity, reproducing the spectroscopic signatures of reversible $\text{Ni}^{\text{I}}/\text{Ni}^{\text{II}}$ cycling and demonstrating that the Ni centers undergo sustained redox transitions under operating conditions. In contrast, $\text{Cu}@\text{CN}_x$ displayed no regeneration of Cu^{II} after catalysis, consistent with the formation of a stabilized, low-coordinate Cu^{I} species that cannot be re-oxidized (Figures S17 and S18). Importantly, x-ray absorption measurements on the same spent catalysts fully corroborate this picture: XANES/EXAFS spectra of spent $\text{Ni}@\text{CN}_x$ closely resemble those of the as-prepared material, confirming the persistence of Ni^{II} in a four-coordinate N_4 environment (Figure S29, Table S5), whereas spent $\text{Cu}@\text{CN}_x$ is dominated by Cu^{I} species and exhibits an EXAFS signature compatible with two-coordinate N_2 binding (Figure S30, Table S5). The convergence of EPR and XAS evidence demonstrates that $\text{Ni}@\text{CN}_x$ preserves a four-coordinate environment and fully reversible $\text{Ni}^{\text{I}}/\text{Ni}^{\text{II}}$ redox cycling under catalytic conditions, whereas the Cu coordination sphere undergoes irreversible collapse to Cu^{I} ; this intrinsic divergence directly accounts for the inactivity of Cu-based SACs and the sustained performance of $\text{Ni}@\text{CN}_x$ across C–N, C–O, and C–S photoredox couplings.

To elucidate the local coordination of Ni^{I} and Cu^{II} , we employed hyperfine spectroscopies. In contrast to x-ray techniques, which

yield coordination numbers and distances averaged over all metal sites, hyperfine methods provide element- and oxidation-state-selective information and are exquisitely sensitive to the immediate ligand environment. This makes them particularly suited to resolving the local geometry of the paramagnetic Ni^{I} and Cu^{II} centers. The CN_x binding site, composed of nitrogen donor atoms, gives rise to hyperfine interactions dependent on coordination geometry, though these are often unresolved in CW-EPR. High-resolution hyperfine techniques recover NMR transitions of nuclei coupled to the electron spin. Figure 3a–c shows orientationally selective EDNMR spectra of Ni^{I} , revealing a strong absorption between 9–40 MHz from strongly coupled ^{14}N nuclei ($A > 2\nu_1$), and a proton peak at ca. 50 MHz. These spectra were simulated at once with complementary X-band Matched HYSORE and Q-band Davies ENDOR experiments (Figure S19) to derive a single set of parameters (Table 1). The broad signals are attributed to four non-equivalent ^{14}N nuclei with couplings from 14–30 MHz, as confirmed by cross-peaks in the $(-,+)$ HYSORE quadrant (Figure S19b). Similarly, Q-band Davies ENDOR was used to characterize the ligand nitrogens in $\text{Cu}^{\text{II}}@\text{CN}_x$. The spectra (Figure 3d–f) show broad lines, modelled with two ^{14}N couplings (Table 1), consistent with Cu^{II} porphyrin-like systems [32, 33]. For both Ni^{I} and Cu^{II} , a proton coupling (~ 10 MHz) is observed, indicating a metal–proton distance of ~ 0.35 nm.

Thus, although Ni and Cu reside in similar MN_4 environments, only Ni undergoes reversible $\text{M}^{\text{II}}/\text{M}^{\text{I}}$ cycling within CN_x , whereas Cu becomes irreversibly trapped in a reduced state.

These redox behaviors rationalise the catalytic outcomes directly. Ni preserves a four-coordinate geometry upon reduction,

FIGURE 4 | Optimized DFT structures for the proposed 3sp [2]_{sp} [3] tetraelem models for Ni^I (a), Ni^{II} (b), Cu^I (c) and Cu^{II} (d), respectively. Computed distances between the N atoms of the melem ligands and the metal center are also reported (Å). Color code for atoms: hydrogen in white, carbon in dark gray, nitrogen in blue, nickel in green and copper in brown.

enabling efficient Ni^{II}/Ni^I cycling under photoredox conditions, whereas Cu^I, constrained by the rigid CN_x framework, relaxes into a linear two-coordinate configuration incompatible with reoxidation. The catalytic experiments therefore illustrate the operational consequences of the underlying geometric constraints.

In order to translate the spectroscopic evidence in atomistic models, we employed DFT calculations aimed at modelling the binding site of the two metals in both oxidation states. Based on the constraints emerging from the EPR data, we consider structures that provide four coordinating nitrogen ligands either at the edges of polymeric structures or through unreacted heptazine molecules [14]. In Figure 4, we present the structures (namely 3sp₂_sp₃) which show the best agreement with the experimental findings, while the other structural models are shown in Figures S20–S28.

In their +2 oxidation state, both Ni and Cu structures display a quasi-planar arrangement of the metal coordinated by four nearly equivalent N nuclei with a dihedral angle of 161° < Φ < 179° (see Supporting Information for further details) and distances Ni–N in the range 1.89–1.97 Å and Cu–N in the range 1.97–2.06 Å (Figure 4b,d). There are two larger N–M–N angles

ranging from 111.3° to 117.3° and two smaller spanning from 62.6° to 68.4°, respectively. While this structure is preserved for reduced Ni^I (with elongated Ni–N bond in the range of 2.02–2.25 Å (Figure 4a)), the coordination of Cu^I changes significantly, resulting in two short (1.93 Å and 1.93 Å) and two long (2.44 Å and 2.91 Å) Cu–N bonds, enforcing a two-coordinate quasi-linear geometry with a N–Cu–N angle of 157.5° (Figure 4c).

We focus on the magnetic interactions of Ni^I and Cu^{II} with the surrounding magnetic nuclei ¹⁴N and ¹H (hyperfine interaction). The computed hyperfine parameters are listed in Supporting Information (Figures S20–S28) for the structures investigated in this work. In the case of Ni^I, one key feature emerging from the experiment is the presence of four inequivalent nitrogen ligands and a proton at a distance of approximately 0.35 nm. The optimised MN₄ model reported in Figure 4a reproduces the spectroscopic evidence, with three of the four coordinating nitrogen ligands—with formally sp² hybridization—belonging to the heptazine rings, while one corresponding to a bridging N atom (with formal sp³ hybridization) between two heptazine units. The computed hyperfine couplings reproduce fairly well the experimentally observed values (Figure S22), moreover, this structure provides a protonated N site at 0.35 nm, which can act as a compensating charge in the hydrogen mediated

redox process. A similar situation holds for Cu^{II}, Figure 4d, whereby the shorter M–N bond distance favors a larger spin delocalization over the ligands and consequent larger hyperfine couplings in good agreement with the experimental values (Table 1).

Importantly, while the four coordinated geometry is retained for the Ni^{II}/Ni^I redox couple, in the case of Cu, reduction from +2 to +1 brings about a significant distortion of the coordination geometry, which may explain the reluctance in the reoxidation of Cu^I (Figure 2) and the suppressed photoredox activity of Cu@CN_x as compared to Ni@CN_x.

In summary, EPR provides detailed insights into the redox chemistry of SACs on CN_x and the local coordination environment of their open-shell electronic states. The isoelectronic Ni^I@CN_x and Cu^{II}@CN_x species exhibit similar local structure with MN₄ square planar coordination. The spectroscopic properties are remarkably similar to those reported for Cu^{II} and Ni^I porphyrins reinforcing the notion that these materials harbour well defined molecular-like single atoms. EPR quantification reveals that the number of redox-active, square-planar coordinated sites is limited and constant irrespective of the overall metal loading. This suggests that CN_x provides only a limited number of redox-active coordination sites. However, Ni@CN_x and Cu@CN_x exhibit distinct redox behavior. While Ni^{II}/Ni^I redox cycling is efficient, Cu^{II}/Cu^I is inhibited. From a ligand-field perspective, Ni^{II} (d⁸, low-spin) adopts a square-planar geometry with an empty d_{x₂y₂} orbital that becomes singly occupied upon reduction to Ni^I while preserving a four-coordinate arrangement. This results in a small inner-sphere reorganisation energy and enables reversible Ni^{II}/Ni^I cycling. In contrast, reduction of Cu^{II} (d⁹) to closed-shell Cu^I (d¹⁰) destabilizes the four-coordinate field and forces relaxation to a low-coordinate, quasi-linear geometry, as confirmed by EXAFS. Returning to a square-planar Cu^{II} N₄ site therefore requires a substantial structural penalty, suppressing redox reversibility. The catalytic inactivity of Cu@CN_x reflects the inability of Cu^I to recover the square-planar geometry required for reoxidation.

Notably, XAFS analysis of spent catalysts is fully consistent with DFT simulations.

The convergence of spectroscopic, computational, and catalytic evidence shows that photocatalytic activity in CN_x-supported SACs is governed by the redox compatibility of the MN₄ site, rather than by the nominal oxidation state of the metal alone. The most plausible active sites are edge-located N₄ motifs, comprising three sp² nitrogen atoms from the CN_x framework and one bridging sp³-coordinating nitrogen, which impose a rigid coordination environment. Within this pocket, only metals that undergo a geometry-preserving M^{II}/M^I transition can sustain reversible redox cycling. By probing the intrinsic electronic structure of these sites under well-defined conditions, EPR/ENDOR and XAS isolate the fundamental redox response of the metal centers, revealing geometric and electronic constraints that persist under catalytic operation despite the complexity of the reaction medium. Redox compatibility within a fixed MN₄ architecture therefore emerges as the decisive criterion for activity. This insight provides a general guideline for selecting metals whose reduced-state coordination preferences match the structural con-

straints of rigid supports and suggests that controlling the density and nature of edge-type MN₄ sites in CN_x offers a rational route to improve redox-active single-atom photocatalysts.

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Conflicts of Interest

The authors declare no conflicts of interest.

Data Availability Statement

The data that support the findings of this study are available from the corresponding author upon reasonable request.

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Supporting Information

Additional supporting information can be found online in the Supporting Information section.

Supporting File 1: Additional experimental, spectroscopic, catalytic, and computational data supporting the conclusions of this work are provided in the Supporting Information, together with the corresponding additional references [34–53].